

Amorphoscapes & Soundtoys

Stanza

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Amorphoscapes

Amorphoscapes by Stanza are interactive, generative, audio visual, digital paintings and drawings created specifically for the internet. This is interactive art on the Internet, incorporating generative sounds and 3D imaging.

What are Amorphoscapes?

Amorphoscapes, provide a seductive, multisensory non-linear and interactive experience for the audience to immerse into. Cellular forms replicate, intricate webs evolve, moods and colours change and fuse, sounds and rhythms pulse and change. Amorphoscapes allow the "user" to experience each artwork differently, depending on how they choose to navigate. As well as providing this non-linearity, some of the pieces change over time, ie they generate. The "user" controls these evolving pieces through movement. The character of the resulting piece is unique to the user. This change in the relationship between the 'user' and the artist changes the perception of the artwork. The user can choose what they experience. At any time the user can make subtle or total change to their amorphoscape whenever they want to explore further. Or simply watch the piece change itself, in a generative way.

Amorphoscapes are audiovisual paintings, and can be installed into 'real' environments, where the movement of people in the room or gallery triggers the interactivity within the work. They could be thought of as drawing and paintings machines, in the future to be projected, onto buildings, on clothes and on cars, and on large plasma screens in your living room. Most of these works have extensive mouse control. As the user moves, the light and the image / lighting changes. To view them go to the website www.amorphoscapes.com. Make sure you let each work download. They all work online within a browser and as such can be defined as net artworks. These pieces are all quite small in file size because they are intended to be accessible to everyone on the net. While the original intention of the amorphoscape series has been for Internet - specific exhibition, more complex pieces may be built and adapted for offline use and exhibition purposes.

Amorphoscapes have been reviewed on ITV in the web review, and featured on sonic artsnet for the gallery channel, soundtoys, rhizome and sonify. 'Generator' was featured on the designers network. They were shown at transmediale in Germany, at cynet art in Dresden. All the works are online and as such are Internet specific artworks. All online at www.amorphoscapes.com. They are not downloadables

or software but exist within the online environment that is the internet.

Soundtoys.net

In recognition of the pioneering experimental works continually being produced by artists for the Internet Soundtoys.net has been established to provide a space for the exhibition of exciting new works by a growing community of audiovisual artists, while also providing a forum for discourse around new technologies and the nature of soundtoys. The site is intended to provide a meeting point for this growing community of artists and users, and in addition to the exhibition of audiovisual projects, the site contains areas for artists interviews, links to resources, and texts by contributing writers where serious issues around interactive arts, audiovisual synthesis, generative art, and a history of interactivity are discussed. Hopefully it is a fun and entertaining site to visit, while also providing valuable information for all parties.

What Are Soundtoys?

Soundtoys (soundtoys.net) may take the form of art, games, generative music, interactive environments, shockwave movies, etc. They could be described as "new audio visual experiences", or multimedia experiments, which explore the parameters of our new media world. They might be described as the fusion of audio and visual output through new technologies made available for the Internet. But because this site intends to encourage the expansion of the possibilities of this new media, hard and exclusive definitions should be avoided, and each contributing artist to the exhibition is invited to provide their own views to help develop the dialectic.

The soundtoys site offers insights into the diverse and creative nature of the web, which is available to today's 'creatives'. Increasing numbers of these artists are exploring, researching and playing within the parameters of the medium: Designers, painters, film makers, installation artists, writers, photographers, printmakers, musicians, each bringing to the online audiovisual domain their own intent, their skillset, their history. So many threads here interweaving to make this rich ever-evolving tapestry. This diversity which is inherent to the internet is reflected not least in the variety of technologies explored in the works showing on the soundtoys site; shockwave, flash, vml, java to name a few. The marriage of the visual to the audio is increasingly becoming a central issue in the development of interactive media on the web. The Internet has become the leading economic and artistic tool for our age. Words like 'emergence' are used to explain the propulsion of these medias into our daily lives. Convergence is used to describe the

meeting of medias, and their the fusion through new technology. Our exhibition series and website is for artists to explore the paradigm of audiovisual practice. It also functions as a fun site where the new and cutting edge of artistic research is exhibited and can be engaged with as online Internet experiences.

The soundtoys site features a journal section which aims to provide a forum for debate around the creative use of new technologies for the internet, past, present and future. All interested parties - artists, writers, programmers, scientists, philosophers - are encouraged to post their related essays, texts, articles and debates, and we envisage that this journal will become a valuable reference and research tool which will inform current practice and future development.

Contributions

Soundtoys is open to artists; designers, musicians, writers and programmers who make (or who are interested in the aesthetics of) interactive web soundtoys, artworks and related texts. Work submitted for the site should explore the use of technology for the advancement of audiovisual communication. At the moment artists can either make special new work for the soundtoys site, or send in existing work(s) that they would like to be featured online at the soundtoys site. Soundtoys is now gaining worldwide exposure. In addition to our online presence, Soundtoys is being promoted at numerous other festivals. The site has been reviewed at Sonar, on the Sonify, in the Independent, and on English TV.